

Quantum Mechanics and Double Conservation

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We suggest that quantum mechanics is concerned with preserving two conservations, one related to a kind of probability and the other to a mechanical balance. These two conservations exist at the level of a single particle and are interlinked. Specifically, the derivative d/dx , which measures the effect of a change in a kind of probability, also measures the associated resistance or impulse for a free particle. For a free particle, the “kind of probability” is $\exp(ipx)$ and $d/dx \exp(ipx) = ip \exp(ipx)$ showing that there is an impulse related to p linked with the probability. In other words, a free particle moves through space in a probabilistic manner related to the resistance associated with the impulse p . These two conservations, a kind of probability and a kind of resistance, lead to two independent equations when one considers continuity at points which change momentum.

We consider again the problem of a photon moving in the x direction which reflects or refracts at an interface along the y axis between n_1 - n_2 (indices of refraction). Classically, probability is conserved i.e. $1 = P(\text{reflect}) + P(\text{refract})$ ((1)). The steady state problem, however, has the appearance of an equilibrium and should have a second conservation, namely one in space, i.e. a balance of pressure. This balance, linear in momentum, however, is the identical equation as ((1)). Thus, there are still two unknowns $P(\text{reflect})$, $P(\text{refract})$ and one equation.

In the quantum case, double conservation may classically be manifested by the same equation. This seems to suggest, we argue, that ((1)) is a consequence of an equation based on p (which is linked to momentum). We try to find this association in two ways. First, we argue that the interface may exist at x_0 and that there are various momenta in the problem, We argue these represent pertinent information which does not appear in ((1)). We suggest that ((1)) seems to be a kind of magnitude equation with p and x_0 information being part of the direction of vectors i.e. p and x_0 may exist in a phase $\exp(i f(p,x))$. Together with the conservation of pressure condition, we argue that $\exp(i f(p,x)) = \exp(ipx)$. This argument, however, implicitly involves consider the phase function $\exp(i f(p,x))$ as a kind of probability.

Alternatively, we consider finding this probability follows from maximizing Shannon's entropy subject to the periodic constraint $\int p(x) dx = 1$, but we investigate why Shannon's entropy form should be used, i.e. what is its physical significance?

Double Conservation and One Dimensional Photon Reflection-Refraction

If one tosses a coin or a die, there is a probability for a result, but no pressure considerations. If one has a photon which moves in the x direction and reflects/refracts at some x_0 due to a y -axis n_1 - n_2 index of refraction interface, there is probability conservation ((1)), but at the same time, different momenta. The incident photon has momentum p , the reflected $-p$, and the refracted $p_2 = n_2 p$ for $n_1 = 1$. In other words, different impulses and pressures are present. If one has a steady state problem, there should exist a second balance, other than ((1)). ((1)) represents conservation of probability in time (and is equivalent to conservation of energy and photon number as $E = pc$ and E is the same for the incident, reflected and refracted photons).

Pressure, from classical mechanics, requires p and a flux. If one defines flux by AA, BB, CC (positive numbers) for the incident, reflected and refracted photons then conservation of pressure is:

$$AAp - p BB = p^2 CC \quad ((2))$$

Using $E=pc$ ((3)), ((2)) becomes: $AA/c1 - BB/c1 = CC/c2 \quad ((3))$

((3)), however, is identical to ((1)) as flux divided by speed yields the number of photons.

This raises two issues. First, one has two unknowns B, C if A is known, and secondly, double conservation is represented by one and the same equation. Furthermore, this double conservation must apply to a single photon, as ((1)) applies to a single entity as well as to a steady stream case. This suggests, we argue, that double conservation is built-in to the description of a single particle with momentum p . The question is: How? We consider two different approaches.

Magnitude Versus Phase and Information

As a first approach, we consider the problem in terms of information. ((1)) does not explicitly contain any information about p or x_0 , the position of the interface. P (momentum) is critical in the problem. x_0 may be shifted and so may be taken to be 0, but it is information and there is no reason why it should not appear. How does one reconcile this lack of information in ((1))? We suggest one may consider ((1)) as a kind of balance of magnitudes, with extra information contained in the direction of vectors involved. In other words, one has magnitudes and phases (but this is only part of the problem). As a start, one may mathematically express the magnitude-phase idea as:

$$\text{Incident photon: } A \exp(i f(p,x)), \text{ Reflected: } B \exp(i f(-p,x)), C \exp(i f(p_2,x)) \quad ((4))$$

with $f(p,x)$ being completely unknown. One may then establish a continuity at x_0 , i.e.

$$A \exp(i f(p,x_0)) + B \exp(i f(-p,x_0)) = C \exp(i f(p_2,x_0)) \quad ((5))$$

((5)), although it includes the extra information p, x , is not solvable because one has no idea what the function f is. We suggest one must consider double conservation, i.e. the presence of a pressure balance. ((5)), however, is not directly linked to a classical pressure equation it seems. In order to solve ((5)), we suggest that motion of a free particle, itself, must be linked with a kind of resistance related to p , momentum. This association should yield a linear p , because impulse is proportional to p , and should result from the operation of d/dx , i.e. changing the probability by dx if in fact there is physical resistance present. This immediately gives a recipe i.e.

$$d/dx \exp(i f(p,x)) = i df/dx = i p G(p,x) \quad ((6))$$

We further suggest that $G(p,x)$ should be $\exp(i f(p,x))$, in order that p be multiplied by the kind of probability present. This leads to $\exp(ipx)$ as a solution. In other words, there is a kind of probability $\exp(ipx)$ present which is directly linked with a resistance (proportional to p) in space. The assumption of $\exp(ipx)$ as a probability is needed to write $G(p,x)$ as $\exp(i f(p,x))$ and justify linking p with d/dx . This begs the question: Can $\exp(ipx)$ result from a maximization of Shannon's entropy? If the answer is yes, a second question follows. Shannon's entropy is associated with $\ln(n!)$ which is the \ln of the number of permutations of n objects. Why should such a form have any physical relevance in the reflection-refraction problem?

First, however, we wish to examine how these ideas affect ((5)) and lead to the solution of the reflection-refraction problem. If one applies d/dx to ((5)), one obtains two independent equations representing the double conservation i.e. ((5)) and:

$$A p \exp(ipx) - B p \exp(-ipx) = C p^2 \exp(ip^2 x) \quad ((7))$$

((7)) is linear in p and so is of the form needed for ((2)), but B in ((7)) is negative for $n_1 < n_2$. Furthermore, one must remove the phases $\exp(ipx)$ etc. To do so one may suggest multiplying the complex conjugate of ((5)) with ((7)). The difference of squares which results ensures mutual exclusivity of events, which we discussed in another note ((1)). Then:

$$A A p - B B p = p^2 C C \quad ((8))$$

((8)) represents the double classical conservation (probability-photon number-energy with pressure).

$\exp(ipx)$ and Maximization of Shannon's Entropy

We have suggested in previous notes that one may obtain $\exp(ipx)$ by maximizing Shannon's entropy subject to the periodic constraint, $\int_0^1 P(x) dx = 1$ i.e.

$$\text{Maximize } -\int_0^1 P(x) \ln(P(x)) dx + i p x \int_0^1 P(x) dx \quad ((9))$$

The question we ask is: Why should Shannon's entropy have anything to do with a reflection-refraction problem? Shannon's entropy essentially uses $\ln(n!)$ where $n!$ is the number of permutations of n objects. Why should this be maximized here? We noted in (2) that maximization of Shannon's entropy followed by taking a derivative yields a balance equation which may be associated with mechanical balance. We suggest that for ((9)), maximizing entropy yields the first conservation equation ($\exp(ipx)$ kind of probability) when combined with other $\exp(ipx)$ s and continuity at a point x , but taking a derivative, e.g. d/dx , and applying continuity, yields the second conservation. In quantum, both equations are key and combine to create the classical probability conservation equation ((1)) with p and x information explicitly removed. As a result, Shannon's entropy yields a certain form for $P(x,p)$ such that the derivative yields a linear p multiplied by probability. A linear p is used in the constraint $\int_0^1 P(x) dx = 1$ because the constraint must be associated with a conserved quantity and it is p which is conserved in

impulse hits. (In classical statistical mechanics, $e=pp/2m$ is used in the constraint and this is linked with pressure balance, even though p , momentum, is still conserved in collisions.) Shannon's entropy form is needed to ensure the relation:

$$d/dx d/dP (\text{entropy}(P(x)) = ip \quad ((10))$$

In other words, the x probability distribution must be such that it maximizes Shannon's entropy, and not some other math function. Intrinsicly, the idea of probability and its relation to a resistance in space through d/dx yielding p and the probability back is directly associated with a Shannon's entropy maximization, i.e. maximization of $P(x)\ln(P(x))$ which is linked with $\ln(n!)$ where $n!$ is the number of permutations of n objects. A priori, this may not be obvious, but if there were some other math function, not Shannon's entropy involved, it means there would be further information linked with a momentum p than just the value of p itself. This, in turn, would give rise to a different scheme which would not return $p \exp(ipx)$ in ((7)) and so might not lead to p and x disappearing to create ((1)).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a one dimensional photon reflection-refraction problem is associated with double conservation. First, there is the usual conservation of probability $P(\text{reflect})+P(\text{refract})=1$, but there are also momentum change and so a steady state picture requires a balance of pressure, i.e. a conservation in space. The issue is that these two conservations are one and the same, leaving two unknowns $P(\text{reflect})$, $P(\text{refract})$ and one equation. We suggest that because the two equations are the same, and because the probability equation holds for a single photon, the motion of a single photon must somehow be linked with p . We argue that both p and x do not appear in ((1)) and suggest that ((1)) may be an equation of magnitudes with vector-type phases disappearing. In other words we suggest the lost information p,x appears in the form $\exp(i f(p,x))$ with amplitudes linked to probabilities. This still leaves no way of determining the unknown $f(p,x)$.

We suggest that if the phase function, $\exp(i f(p,x))$, is associated with a probability in space and also a resistance due to p , then d/dx should pick out this resistance, i.e. yield p proportional to impulse multiplied by probability i.e. $d/dx \exp(i f(p,x)) = ip \exp(i f(p,x))$. This yields the form $\exp(ipx)$.

Given that probability arguments must be introduced, we ask whether $\exp(ipx)$ follows from maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to a constraint. We argue it does and suggest Shannon's entropy maximization and its derivative yield double conservation. In other words, the two independent equations are strongly linked (through d/dx) and lead to one classical equation which does not show x or p i.e. ((1)).

Furthermore, Shannon's entropy maximizes $\ln(n!)$ where $n!$ is the number of permutations of n objects. This is an attempt to remove information (i.e. have maximum randomness). This approach yields the p balance needed, i.e. ensures that there are no other physical rules influencing the balance involving p (impulse).

References

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